

26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators
"From Global Indicators to Local Applications"

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STI 2022 Conference Proceedings

Proceedings of the 26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators

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Citation: Sastron-Toledo P., & De Filippo, D. (2022). Relations between scientific activity and public policy in the field of open science. The case of Spain. In N. Robinson-Garcia, D. Torres-Salinas, & W. Arroyo-Machado (Eds.), *26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators*, STI 2022 (sti2228). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6960078>

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26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators | STI 2022

“From Global Indicators to Local Applications”

7-9 September 2022 | Granada, Spain

#STI22GRX

Relations between scientific activity and public policy in the field of open science. The case of Spain¹

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Introduction

The Open Science movement has gained special relevance in recent years, generating a paradigm shift in how scientific knowledge is produced and disseminated. Different institutions have developed numerous policies and strategies for its promotion and consolidation. The European Union has been one of the leading global promoters (Anglada and Abadal, 2018), through the adoption of open access in 2012 and the development of initiatives such as *OpenAire*, the creation of the *European Open Science Cloud* (EOSC) and the development of the *Open Science Monitor*.

The European Commission's recommendations have guided the development of policies by numerous countries, such as Finland (Forsström and Haataja, 2016), the Netherlands (Netherlands, 2017), Portugal (Portugal, 2016) and Spain (Spain, 2017).

In this context, Mohammadi and Thelwall (2013) stated that the multiplication of informal communication channels poses a new challenge to the analysis of scientific activity.

In this sense, bibliometrics' traditional toolbox for evaluating scientific activity has been expanded for a little over a decade by the addition of altmetric indicators (Priem and Hemminger, 2010) to analyse scientific production's impact on non-scientific audiences. International bodies have taken up this challenge through various reports and recommendations (European Commission, 2017a; 2017b; 2018; Wouters et al., 2019).

The aim of this study is, first, to analyse Spanish institutions' scientific activity on open science -measured mainly in terms of scientific publications- and, second, to study the impact of these publications on non-academic audiences. In addition to identifying and analysing what characteristics these publications have, we will study how publications on open science are incorporated into the field of public policy through citations.

¹ This work was supported under "The Role of Open Science in the Spanish University: Institutional Transformation and Anticipatory Governance" (ROSSUE, PID2019-104052RB-C21), a project financed by the Spanish State Research Agency under the National RDI Plan's RETOS call.

Sources

Two sources of information were used:

- Clarivate Analytics' Web of Science database to detect and analyse scientific publications on open science.
- Overton database to relate policy documents with scientific documents through citations.

Methodology

First, a keyword-based search strategy was defined to identify scientific publications on open science, designed on the basis of a review of the scientific literature and validated by experts in the field (De Filippo and Lascurain, 2021).

Once the publications signed by at least one Spanish institution had been retrieved, bibliometric indicators of scientific activity, specialisation, collaboration, impact and visibility were obtained.

Finally, the DOIs of the publications were extracted and queried into the Overton search engine to obtain citation indicators in policy documents. It was necessary to review and debug the results because, although the tool performs a disambiguation exercise to eliminate duplicates, many duplicates slip through because they do not have unique identifiers (DOI, ISSN) and they come from different URLs.

Results

We identified 913 publications on open science signed by Spanish institutions from 2011 to 2020. Spain's contribution to world production on the subject has been growing; it reached 6% in 2020 (Figure 1). Spain ranks 7th in the world behind the USA (31%), China (15%), England (14%), Germany (7%), Canada (7%) and Australia (6%).

Figure 1. Scientific production on open science

The topics with the highest concentration of documents were Library and Information Science, Computer Sciences and the Environment. The Spanish National Research Council was the organisation with the highest production (89 publications), although Spanish universities participated in approximately 82% of the documents.

Of the total number of documents with DOIs (877), 128 publications (14%) were cited in policy documents. These publications were published in 88 journals, 8 of which accounted for a quarter of the publications. Table 1 shows that some titles related to the environmental field had one third of their open science publications cited in policy documents.

Table 1. Journals with the highest number of papers cited in policy sources

Journal	No. of publications in policy docs.	%	No. of publications on open science	%
El Profesional de la Información	10	7.87	72	13.89
Research Policy	4	3.15	7	57.14
Revista española de Documentación Científica	4	3.15	19	21.05
Ecology and Society	3	2.36	4	75.00
Ecosystem Services	3	2.36	4	75.01
Journal of Apicultural Research	3	2.37	4	75.02
Science and Public Policy	3	2.38	5	60.00
Science of the Total Environment	3	2.39	6	50.00

Almost half of the citing organisations were government bodies; the other half were mostly divided between IGOs and think tanks, and the remaining 2% were other types of institutions. In particular, the Publications Office of the European Union was the organisation that cited the most Spanish documents about open science (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Types of institutions citing Spanish open science publications

The countries citing Spanish publications on open science were the United States, Germany, Belgium and Spain itself. However, policy documents from multinational entities and the European Union accounted for the most significant proportion of citations of Spanish publications on open science (Figure 2). The percentage of documents cited in open access was 56%.

Figure 3. Countries citing Spanish open science publications

Discussion

The results show that scientific publications on open science have grown steadily in the last decade, as observed in other previous studies (De Filippo; Da Silva and Borges, 2019). The countries with the largest published scientific output, such as the United States, China and the United Kingdom, are also the countries with the largest published output about open science. Still, there are other countries, such as Australia, the Netherlands, South Africa and Finland, whose open science activity is intense. This fact coincides with the implementation (since 2011/2012) of European and national policies focused on promoting and consolidating the Open Science movement. In the specific case of Spain, while the country ranks 10th in the world by total production in the Web of Science, it holds position 7 in the field of open science, which evinces the academic community's interest in the subject in the wake of numerous initiatives also rolled out in the last decade (De Filippo and Mañana-Rodríguez, 2022).

The topics most closely related to open science were Computer Science and Library and Information Science, since many of the publications analysed technical aspects related to open access to information, the interconnection of different data sources, etc.

Although the CSIC was the main producer of publications among Spanish research centres, the Spanish higher education system was responsible for the largest number of documents about open science. In this sense, Overton is a particularly good tool for analysing documents on social science, economics and the environment, disciplines in which it has wide coverage (Szomszor & Adie, 2022; Pinheiro et al., 2021). Fourteen percent of Spanish publications on open science were referenced in policy documents, especially documents put out by government bodies in general and the European Union in particular. Although there is a bias in the source with respect to the representation of policy bodies from North American and European countries (Szomszor & Adie, 2022), the results seem consistent with reality, since Spanish production is used in publications from the European Union, North America and Latin America and is also an important input for Spanish ministries' policy documents.

At the technical level, one of the limitations encountered was the duplication of results. Exclusion of the duplicates (15%) required manual review.

Despite these limitations, this study has served as a starting point for further analysis of the different modes of open science production and communication. We are currently developing new methodologies to retrieve different types of activities related to open science and to measure their impact on social actors.

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